

Reuse of qualitative research data - community developments and needs

Report on the results of a survey conducted at a Data Stewards
Interest Group meeting

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Summary

This document provides a report of the results of a survey conducted at the February 2023 meeting of the Data Stewards Interest Group, which focused on the CaRe&DaRe project. The project team hosted a survey at this meeting to gather input from the qualitative data community on their experiences, challenges, and needs. This will be used to create a guidance document for qualitative researchers and data stewards with the aim of increasing the amount of qualitative data that is well documented and shared for reuse whenever possible, as well as offering options in situations where sharing is less straightforward.

This report introduces the CaRe&DaRe and follow-up projects that will focus on the reuse of qualitative data, as well as the Data Stewards Interest Group and the role of DANS. Next, this document presents the results from the survey DANS held during the meeting to gather community input. The report finishes with some details on the next steps for DANS in this project and the envisioned guidance to be produced and shared.

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Background

CaRe&DaRe

The CaRe&DaRe project, 'Case-study Research and Data Reuse'¹, focuses on increasing and better facilitating the reuse of qualitative data in science. Funded by the NWO Open Science Fund², the one-year project is a collaboration between the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU)³, SURF⁴, and DANS⁵. It aims to initiate a novel method for making data that cannot be openly shared due to confidentiality restrictions reusable. This project will be followed-up by the longer running OPEN-QUAL, Innovating Methods for Open Science in Qualitative Management Research⁶, where this methodology will be further developed and tested.

Qualitative data is often overlooked in the fast-paced developments of Open Science, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data, and general Research Data Management (RDM). Qualitative data sharing is often more complex or impossible to facilitate, since anonymisation can often lead to information losses, and it can be hard to capture all the contextual information that is essential for the interpretation of qualitative data. Taken together, researchers often neglect qualitative data when it comes to archiving, sharing, or reusing. This results in a loss of opportunity, since the production of qualitative data can be quite time- and resource intensive and often results in the generation of data which cannot be reproduced in a different setting (e.g., lived experiences). These features make qualitative data an excellent candidate for long term preservation and reuse⁷. Funder demands for FAIR and open data pose a growing challenge for qualitative researchers, and without effective reuse efforts are being depleted in highly similar studies.

The alternative to this current status quo that the CaRe&DaRe and OPEN-QUAL projects aim to offer is that of *decentralised re-analysis and reuse*. Using this method, researchers can offer information about their qualitative data (but not the data itself) for sharing. Based on this, interested reusers can approach the original researchers with an analysis protocol that fits their proposed study. The original researchers can then execute this protocol on their data and send back the results of this, so that the reuser has new data for their study without the original sensitive data leaving the environment of the original researcher. This method allows for reuse of qualitative data when sharing data is not an option. The projects also aim to improve the FAIRness of qualitative data by asking researchers to provide metadata on their research and describe the studies in such a way that their reuse potential can easily be evaluated by other researchers. Such approaches of decentralised re-analysis and reuse can facilitate cross-case analysis and prevent qualitative researchers from uselessly repeating studies already executed previously, thus saving valuable time and resources. In CaRe&DaRe, a pilot study has been done using this methodology. The lessons learned on

¹ Project information about CaRe & DaRe <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/203001153> [accessed 24-02-2023]

² Information about the Open Science fund <https://www.nwo.nl/en/researchprogrammes/open-science/open-science-fund> [accessed 24-02-2023]

³ Website of the VU <https://vu.nl/en> [accessed 24-02-2023]

⁴ Website of SURF <https://www.surf.nl/en> [accessed 24-02-2023]

⁵ Website of DANS <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/> [accessed 24-02-2023]

⁶ Project information about OPEN-QUAL <https://www.nwo.nl/en/projects/40621eb014> [accessed 24-02-2023]

⁷How to Appraise and Select Research Data for Curation <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides/appraise-select-data> [accessed 24-02-2023]

the formulation of the analytical protocol, rules of engagement, and other aspects of the process will be taken along to OPEN-QUAL to be further developed.

DANS

As one of the partners in CaRe&DaRe, DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services, an institute of KNAW and NWO) focuses its efforts on providing information and guidance on the data management of qualitative data as well as on making and keeping it FAIR. As the national centre of expertise on research data, DANS has acquired knowledge on all types of data through (inter)national projects and collaborations. As a repository, DANS holds a collection of qualitative data deposits that are being curated and preserved for the long term. DANS is an avid supporter of developments that increase the amount of data that is being made FAIR and as well as preserved and curated for the long term to facilitate reuse of data.

To aid the development of the *decentralised reuse* methodology in the CaRe&DaRe project, DANS is working on guidelines that address the metadata needed for qualitative studies to provide information that allows other researchers to evaluate their potential for reuse in new research questions. Furthermore, information and guidance will be produced for the community of qualitative researchers and data stewards, to help these stakeholders design studies where the data is FAIR by design and reuse options can be easily assessed. To gather input from the community to steer the development of these guidelines, a group of data stewards at a Data Stewards interest Group meeting were polled.

Data Stewards Interest Group

Established by the Leiden UMC, UMC Utrecht, and DTL, the Data Stewards Interest Group⁸ facilitates a community hub for data stewardship that enables informal and inclusive knowledge and experience exchange. Through (virtual) meetings, data stewards from all different contexts and backgrounds can come together to exchange recent developments and discuss topics in which they have a shared interest. The community also interacts through a mailing list and slack community, and has some Special Interest Groups in which more dedicated goals can be achieved⁹. The February 2023 meeting¹⁰, the 31st meeting of the group, was dedicated to the CaRe&DaRe project.

With an audience of over 60 people, the meeting was well attended. Many new members also joined this meeting for the first time. The meeting was chaired by Kacana Khadjavi¹¹ and Eric Haynes¹² from the VU, who both work on the project. After the usual social introductions and updates on new and newsworthy items, the CaRe&DaRe project was introduced to the

⁸ Data Stewards interest group <https://www.dtls.nl/about/community/interest-groups/data-stewards-interest-group/> [accessed 24-02-2023]

⁹ You can sign up for the DSIG community on the group's page free of charge. All meeting notes are freely accessible for anyone.

¹⁰ The meetings minutes are publicly accessible here: https://docs.google.com/document/d/18XdcUlg5I4LZ_aZKZPvCIUlgqLXOT-iPtmFk0LPvSkA/edit?usp=sharing

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audience by project lead Hans Berends¹³ (VU), followed by a group discussion where data stewards could pose questions and input for the project. This resulted in interesting discussions both live and in the chat, where different situations and questions were talked through and solutions and answers were provided. In the last part of the meeting, Maaïke Verburg (DANS) hosted a Mentimeter survey to capture information from the community on the current resources and desires with regards to the management of qualitative data. The survey remained open for responses for a few days after the meeting to allow the audience to provide all their desired information.

This report presents the outcomes from this survey and the implications of this community response.

Results

The Mentimeter survey was filled in by 64 respondents in total, with varying response rates for each question. In this section all results from the survey will be discussed.

The first question asked to give an indication of the domain(s) the respondents work in. Sixty-one respondents answered this question and the results can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Results for the question 'What domain(s) do you work in?'

It was possible to indicate multiple domains for this question, which several respondents did ($n=10$, 16%). Most respondents worked in the life, health, and medical sciences or the social sciences and humanities.

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The next question (answered by 60 respondents) focused on some situations and data types the respondents could encounter in their work: qualitative data, sensitive data, interdisciplinary data, reservations about data sharing, and (funder) demands for data sharing. Respondents answered on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 'Very little' to 'A lot'. Results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Results for the question 'How much do you encounter the following in your work?'

The scores presented for each row in the figure depict the average scores. The shading in the background shows the distribution of the different scores. From this, we can gather that all topics are encountered quite often in the work of these respondents, with sensitive data occurring most often. The distributions generally show no great deviations from the average, though in almost all cases a part respondents indicated considerably higher occurrences.

These results reiterated in the first place that the audience of the meeting often encounter qualitative data and are therefore the desired audience we want to address in the project. Moreover, we reestablished that people working with qualitative data often encounter sensitive data, and also that sensitive data is encountered more often, indicating the cases where quantitative data can be sensitive as well. Interdisciplinary data is also encountered to some extent. The general trend of an increased focus on data sharing can also be seen in these results, with reservations about data sharing surpassing the experienced demands for the sharing of data. Reservations are observed in many cases still, and given the added complexities of qualitative data, it is no surprise that this is often encountered by our respondents.

Qualitative data types

The next question asked respondents to indicate what types of qualitative data they encounter in their work. Respondents could enter up to 10 different answers to give insight into the wide

Figure 4. A bar chart presenting the frequencies of the main categories of answers submitted by respondents to the question ‘What types of qualitative data do you encounter?’

Challenges

The next question asked was ‘What challenges do you encounter when applying the principles and practices of general research data management or open science to qualitative data?’. For this open question, 34 respondents gave a total of 53 answers. The answers were again grouped in main categories (e.g., ‘Privacy’, ‘GDPR’, ‘Sensitive data’ are all grouped under the main category ‘GDPR’) to give an indication of general trends. Figure 5 shows that the answers can be approximately grouped into six categories: GDPR, anonymisation, lack of guidance, sovereignty, effort, and no data.

The **GDPR** category proved the most frequently encountered challenge. This includes considerations to be made regarding data sharing when dealing with personal or sensitive

data, how to navigate the creation of informed consent forms that could allow for data sharing, how to ethically deal with participants' rights (e.g., the right to retract permissions or to be deleted). Data stewards also encounter such issues when trying to convince researchers to share their data when it is possible. Researchers can often be too careful, not wanting to share even when there is consent, or when data is anonymised.

Anonymisation is a challenge on its own, since qualitative data can suffer great losses of value when certain pieces of information are deleted or altered. This experience is at the core of the CaRe&DaRe project and the methodology of *decentralised reuse* might be a solution for respondents who encounter these challenges.

Figure 5. Column chart indicating the frequencies of the main categories of answers submitted by respondents to the question 'What challenges do you encounter when applying RDM or open science to qualitative data?'

Related to the other topics, a general challenge experienced by respondents is a **lack of guidance**. There is a desire for documentation or other resources that can help navigate data sharing and anonymisation. In some communities there is also a need for better established community standards, so the data can be handled and made FAIR according to such standards. Standard workflows or decision making tools are generally desired.

The concepts of **sovereignty** and ownership also came up as a challenge when it comes to RDM and Open Science for qualitative data. Researchers can often be concerned about potential misinterpretation or misuse of their data, or feel that other researchers would lack certain contextual knowledge, causing loss of value of the data. These concerns and challenges are not unique to qualitative researchers, but there may be more focus on the essential contextual information that may be less important for quantitative research. This

could also be a case where *decentralised reuse* provides a possible solution, as the data remains with the original researchers and thus also with their contextual knowledge of the study. However, providing clear documentation and metadata is also of great importance when needing to convey contextual information about data. The latter approach is preferable, as even original researchers can lose their grasp on contextual information of a certain study or dataset over time. Making sure data is clearly documented and accompanied by rich metadata can ensure that everyone interacting with the data has a clear understanding of its correct interpretation and use.

This does lead to the next challenge often observed: the amount of **effort** it takes to properly prepare data for sharing. Again, this is not a unique challenge to qualitative data, but since contextual information and metadata is of such importance, this can take quite some effort to get right. As can be seen from Figure 5, this perceived or experienced effort is often encountered as a challenge when applying research data management and Open Science practices to qualitative data. This ties in with the need for guidance to lower the effort, by providing assistance in decision making or tools to achieve certain tasks more easily.

The last category is a challenge more unique to qualitative research. There can be the perception that there is '**no data**' resulting from qualitative research, or at least not anything that should be handled in the same way as a database full of numbers should be. Researchers tend to think qualitative data is so overlooked that all general research data management practices were not designed to apply to them and that they therefore, for example, do not need to create a data management plan or try to archive and share their data. For data stewards, it can be quite a challenging task to assist researchers in RDM when they do not think they have data in their possession.

Documentation

Next, the audience was asked about the documentation and metadata that should accompany a qualitative dataset so that it can be effectively reused. Respondents were asked to answer based on their own experiences and focus on the qualities that are more unique to qualitative data. For this question, 23 respondents provided a total of 40 answers. Figure 6 shows the answers in a similar way as the previous open questions, with answers grouped on some main categories.

In line with what has been established earlier on in the report, the most important information that respondents identified for facilitating reuse of qualitative data is context information and provenance. This is also reflected in some of the other categories, such as methodology and protocol. Respondents also mentioned community standards, which is an important FAIR practice for enabling interoperability and reusability. Some respondents also indicated they had no knowledge of the needed information and documentation, again suggesting a need for better guidance and information.

Figure 6. Bar chart presenting the frequencies of the main categories of answers submitted by respondents to the question ‘What information is needed about a qualitative dataset to facilitate reuse?’

Resources

Respondents were asked about the resources they currently have available to them for working with and sharing qualitative data. This gave the community the opportunity to exchange knowledge and useful resources to help each other out in this topic. Nine respondents shared some resources, which are listed below in Table 1. Based on the submitted answers, we have collected information about each tool to explain its purpose, link to the resource, and provide some comments and considerations about them.

Table 1. List of resources supplied by the respondents for working with and sharing qualitative data.

Resource	Link	Purpose	Comments
ATLAS.ti	https://atlasti.com/	AI tools to uncover qualitative insights in your data	This is a commercial paid service with different licence types available

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG)	https://dmeg.cessda.eu/	A guide for making research FAIR	This resource is not specific to qualitative data, but much of the information is relevant and applicable. Focus is on social science, but can also be used by wider communities.
Repositories	You can use https://re3data.org/ to search repositories to fit your needs/standards	Sharing data can be accomplished by archiving it in a repository. The repository will also care for the data for the long term, to make sure it's preserved.	Repositories can take over a lot of the work to make data FAIR and to facilitate Open Science. To do so, researchers have to select a trustworthy archive which sustainably provides these services (e.g., a certified trustworthy digital repository)
Qualitative Data Repository (QDR) Services and Guides	https://qdr.syr.edu/qdr-services	Several guides, services, and tips for working with qualitative and/or sensitive data	QDR is a dedicated archive for qualitative data.
Anonymisation Guides	E.g., https://www.eur.nl/en/research/research-services/research-data-management/anonymisation-research-data or https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/anonymisation/anonymising-qualitative-data/	Guides provided by organisations on how to anonymise research data	Be mindful that not all guides will be specific to qualitative data.
Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) standards	https://ddialliance.org/	Metadata standard - mainly used for data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioural, economic, and health sciences.	DDI standards are free to use and are the standard in many communities. You can also use DDI to generate codebooks, data catalogues, and build question banks.
Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model (CDM)	https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/	A standard to standardise the structure and content of observational data and enable efficient analysis, focused mostly on medical science.	This is an open community standard. The OMOP model works with the Observation Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) standard vocabularies for medical terms.
YODA Research Data Management Service	https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/display/WIKI/Yoda+Hosting	A data management service from Utrecht University to deposit, share, publish and preserve data during all stages of a research project.	This service is only available for researchers at an organisation with an implementation of YODA and their collaborators.

Needs

Lastly, respondents were asked about their needs for navigating qualitative data. This is where the project team was able to collect direct input for the guidance DANS is intending to create for the community. Ten respondents answered this last question and shared what needs they currently have when it comes to working with qualitative data. The answers were captured in the following list:

- Information on licences for qualitative data
- Information and guidelines on qualitative data sharing
- A centralised place for data to be shared
- Checklist with tips and tricks for researchers working with qualitative data
- Advice on what to take into account during the design phase of research when doing qualitative research
- Example datasets and examples of successful reuse of qualitative data
- Information and guidance on metadata for qualitative data

One respondent also pointed out that an important question to be asking is whether qualitative researchers see themselves and their research reflected in existing research infrastructures, and, if this is not the case, what kind of infrastructure they imagine could address their needs.

Conclusion and next steps

This report was created to openly share an overview of the community input the CaRe&DaRe project received from the Data Stewards Interest Group regarding RDM and Open Science for qualitative research. DANS intends to address some of the challenges, questions, and needs expressed in the survey in the outputs we will create within the CaRe&DaRe and OPEN-QUAL projects. We aim to disseminate materials and knowledge within the community so they can be effectively used by all data stewards and researchers who are working with sensitive data. *Decentralised reuse* is developed in these projects as a way to reuse data in specific situations where other options are not available or preferred. We will make sure to give the community insights into all the different options available to data producers when sharing qualitative (and personal) data. We hope to foster the practice of qualitative data sharing by informing when this may be more easily possible than it seems. We will also include useful tools, guides, resources, and examples to consider when working with and sharing qualitative data. Taken together, we hope to present useful information for qualitative researchers and data stewards that they can use to be able to adhere to (funder) demands, or satisfy other open science, FAIR data, and data management practices. Once this guidance has been developed, it will be published on Zenodo and promoted through the Data Steward Interest Group.